

MARKETING PROBLEMS IN AGRICULTURAL EXPORT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article presents practical studies on the assessment of trends in the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan and identification of export problems, as well as the relationship between agricultural franchise structures and advertising, marketing and consulting services.*

Keywords: *agro-industrial complex, agriculture, reform, competition, food, agribusiness, forestry, fisheries, agriculture, animal husbandry, agromarketing.*

Introduction. in the Republic of Uzbekistan Agricultural marketing is different from industrial, commercial, banking and other types of marketing. It is related to the characteristics of agriculture. The results depend on the natural conditions, the role and importance of the product, the variety of forms of ownership, the incompatibility of the labor period and the production period, the seasonality of production and production, and the variety of organizational forms of economic management. their dialectic. Participation of Russia, foreign economic relations, agro-industrial complex and state bodies in the development of their industries. In the agro-industrial complex, natural and economic processes are combined, creating special conditions for the organization of production and sale of products.

Marketing activities in agricultural and agro-industrial structures will be effective only if all management personnel participate in it and all production personnel support them. in livestock enterprises, for example, the functional marketing effect is carried out by both the head of the enterprise and the head of the farm. Economists, technologists and others take part in this along with marketers, animal husbandry experts. Along with management staff, marketing functions are performed by production staff. They produce products of the required quality, of the specified assortment, and create conditions for timely satisfaction of consumer demand.

Analysis of literature on the topic Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application. Among them, we can include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the marketing theory in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, M. Boltaboev, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Today, comprehensive measures are being implemented in our country aimed at expanding the production, storage, processing and export of fruits and vegetables. In order to implement the projects of rapid development of fruit and vegetable production, the territory was significantly expanded, additional facilities for storage and processing of fruit and

vegetable products were launched, financial resources, including funds from international financial institutions, were attracted. actively participates. For example, in January-December 2023, 8% of investments worth 189,924.3 billion soums were directed to agriculture. As a result, the volume of production of agricultural products this year is 215.7 trillion soums or 102.7 percent compared to the level of 2022, including agricultural products - 108.3 trillion soums (103.7 percent), livestock products - 107.4 trillion soums (101.7 percent).

The role of marketing in the export of agricultural products can also be seen from the characteristics of these products. First of all, the rapid aging of products determines their short-term sales period. In addition, the appearance of the product requires a lot of attention to packaging that meets the standard of this market. Add to this the consideration of sanitary requirements, and we see how important marketing is in the export of vegetables and fruits. It can be seen that in the organization of the sale of fruit and vegetable products in countries with a developed market economy, producers quickly and correctly study the changes in consumer demand and take appropriate measures. Therefore, for marketing to be successful in agricultural enterprises, business managers must clearly define goals, make decisions based on reliable information about their current financial and financial situation. In general, rather than relying on export infrastructure, farmers themselves should plan and implement marketing activities.

In our opinion, the current state of marketing of fruit and vegetable products should force the managers of agricultural enterprises to find answers to the following questions in order to assess their position in the domestic and foreign markets and ultimately determine the sales strategy:

- what changes are taking place in foreign markets, how competitive forces affect them;
- how the enterprise works, ie. whether it is necessary to analyze the current state of the enterprise;
- why it occupies the low price segment of the market selling export agricultural products;
- what needs to be done to increase product quality and export potential to increase profits;
- whether a business plan is developed for each product released and whether this plan is analyzed in the supply chain of the product to the consumer.

In many network enterprises, marketing tasks are assigned to certain external structures, which is completely wrong. External infrastructure entities should not only engage in marketing activities, but also help farmers to increase their export potential. The concept of marketing in agriculture as a business philosophy needs to develop a vision that requires the support of all workers and employees in the network.

In recent years, active reforms in the field of agriculture have been implemented in our country. In this regard, a number of decrees and decisions were adopted in order to improve the management system, introduce effective mechanisms of state support, establish cooperation, introduce modern resource-saving technologies, and increase the volume of export of agricultural products. However, at a time when the volume of sales of fruit and vegetable products in the world market was 205 billion US dollars, the share of the republic in this market [less than one percent](#). The share of these products in the country's exports only [7 percent](#) forms.

Uzbekistan has a huge potential for the development of fruit and vegetable production (cultivation) and their export to the foreign market. But it should not be forgotten that potential and its realization are two different concepts. Currently, a lot of work is being done in Uzbekistan to increase agricultural production, but the increase in production does not lead to an increase in

export volume. The reason is that when exporting, first of all, it is necessary to understand what kind of product the potential consumer needs and what he needs. It should also answer questions such as who the real consumer is and in which countries they live. Also, when it comes to fruit exports,

For example, in the European Union, there is almost no demand for vegetables and fruits that do not belong to the "premium" category. A similar situation is observed in the United States and many other developed countries. In addition, each country has its own requirements and needs for different characteristics of fruits in terms of color, taste, size and other characteristics.

Currently, 99 percent of the fruits and vegetables grown in Uzbekistan are of interest only in Russia and the CIS countries. Even in Russia, the market for these products is shrinking, because its main consumers are elderly people. The young generation does not want to buy traditional Uzbek grapes. They focus not on grapes in wooden boxes covered with gauze, but on world-famous seedless varieties sold in convenient packages.

As a result of the reforms implemented in our country in recent years, positive changes are being observed in agriculture. (Table 1). As can be seen from the table, the volume of production increases due to the reduction of the land area.

Table-1

The volume of production of agricultural products in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2023

	2019	2020	2021 year	2022	2023 year
Land for agricultural crops, thousand ha	3694.2	3706.7	3474.5	3396.0	3309.4
Agricultural products, bln	99604.6	115599.2	148199.3	187425.6	216283.1
including:					
Agriculture	55429.2	61755.1	83303.4	98406.4	111904.8
animal husbandry	44175.4	53844.1	64895.9	89019.2	104378.3
Growth rate of agricultural products in percentage compared to last year	106.1	106.3	101.0	100.2	103.3
including:					
Agriculture	105.5	105.7	98.2	95.8	104.8
animal husbandry	106.9	107.0	104.1	105.7	101.6

If you look at comparable prices, the industry experienced positive dynamics in 2020-2021, i.e. the growth rate was at least 6%.

Foreign trade turnover. In recent years, the reforms carried out by the government to promote exports, optimize imports and ensure balanced foreign trade in general will increase the foreign trade turnover of our country to 42.2 billion US dollars and 8.7 billion US dollars by 2023, or 26.2 percent increase. This result was recorded as the highest result in the history of the country. Exports to the ACT were \$17.9 billion. US dollars (growth rate - 128.0%), and the volume of

imports is 24.3 billion. It was USD (growth rate – 124.9%). 6.4 billion during the reporting period. The passive foreign trade balance was reflected in US dollars.

The extensive use of intermediary services in the sale of products produced by most producers is the main factor influencing consumer prices. They are also more interested in market size and price changes, as intermediaries study consumer markets after the product has been produced. Therefore, the share of producers in the price structure of products sold to the market is on average 45-50 percent. The final price is determined by additional interest rates for services provided by other organizations. In particular, the average interest rate in transport is 17-18 percent, in the wholesale market 20-25 percent, and in the retail market 15-20 percent.

In fact, providing the population with original (natural) agricultural products, especially in the autumn-winter season, as well as studying the effect of seasonal changes in market prices on the consumer's ability to pay in these periods is one of the important issues. . . One of the main factors that cause changes in market prices is the release of products to the markets without a clear forecast of consumer demand. In fact, the lack of a fully developed mechanism for solving this problem has led to seasonal changes in consumer prices, sharp changes in prices compared to winter and spring seasons.

In current practice, not only the increase in the volume of agricultural food products, but also the factors affecting the effectiveness of the activity of buyers and sellers in farmers' and peasant farms require taking into account and analyzing the interests of this category of subjects. They are, firstly, the growth of the population creates the basis for the growth of consumer demand; secondly, the increase in household income, while encouraging the purchase of relatively high-quality goods, increases their demand for additional services at the time of purchase; thirdly, such as the convenient location of sales outlets and the conditions of service, taking into account the wishes of consumers.

The following analytical data and suggestions for improving the system of selling agricultural products were included:

Distribution channel through the processing plant:

Pros:

- guaranteed buyer; - Advance payment; - legal security; - Availability of a specific market for a specific variety (fruit, viticulture).

Disadvantages:

unsatisfactory terms and form of payment; - low purchase price or disproportionate quality of goods; - lack of incentives for recycling; - monopoly position

Offer. Ensure that the purchase price in the contract changes daily based on supply and demand. Movement mechanism. On the exact date of delivery, the price should be created according to the database proposed above. In this case, a 10% preference may be in the refinery's interest if there is a guaranteed buyer.

Sales channel through the point of sale:

Pros:

- has relatively high purchasing power; - special packaging, good appearance and relatively long shelf life; - transport and other facilities

Disadvantages:

- impossibility of direct coverage of farms; - there is no demand for low-quality products; - low volume and scattered space

Offer. Establishment of an agricultural franchise. Movement mechanism. It is advisable to organize and advertise the shelves of goods offered under certain brands and trademarks in large shopping centers.

Sales channel through farmers markets:

Pros:

the form of payment (cash) is suitable for the manufacturer; - organization of wholesale trade at a convenient time for the gardener; - Compatibility with shopping culture

Disadvantages:

- sharp difference between wholesale and retail prices; - lack of information about market capacity; - weakness of the market infrastructure

Offer. Creating a database of wholesale markets. Movement mechanism. A database based on modern technologies is created at the entrance to wholesale markets or on convenient shelves. The daily product is given to the intermediary in case of increased supply

Sales channel through intermediaries:

Pros:

- to have daily information about demand, supply and price; - relative superiority of cars in terms of ease of transportation; - Offer small products.

Disadvantages:

- relatively cheap purchase; - violation of producer-consumer relations; - low level of competitive confidence; - based on daily activities.

Offer. Legal organization of mediation services. Movement mechanism. It is necessary to establish a system of legal mediation services, to create a support system for farms located at a certain distance. In this case, priority should be given to the fact that the legal status serves the purpose of support

Sales channel through fairs:

Pros:

- creating a favorable environment and conditions for entering the market; - the ability to quickly attract the attention of consumers; - Creating a "national brand" by offering under the name of a specific region.

Disadvantages:

- dissatisfaction with the payment system; - the mechanism of compensation of "lost money" when selling at prices below the market price is not clear; - problems with the availability of registration and registration from the seller

Offer. Creation of a financial incentive mechanism for fair participants. Movement mechanism. Loss calculation methods can be developed and incentive mechanisms can be introduced for products offered at relatively low prices. For example, buying resources of the same value at preferential prices.

Sales channel through exporters:

Pros:

- a relatively high price for a quality product; - the possibility of selling products from the field (at home); - variety, improved packaging

Disadvantages:

increase sensitivity to changes in foreign and domestic policies; - high emissions in a strong competitive environment; - no purchase guarantee for next season.

Offer. Improvement of the insurance system of products intended for export. Movement mechanism. Implementation of the practice of reimbursing funds lost due to the sale of products grown for export in the domestic market together with "Uzagroexport" and "Uzagrosugurta".

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